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Principals' Leadership Styles and Public Senior Secondary Schools Administrative Effectiveness in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between principals' leadership styles and administrative effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The role of school principals is crucial in creating an environment that fosters effective teaching and learning, and their leadership styles have a significant impact on the overall functioning and success of the school. A mixed method approach is utilized, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. Data from 629 principals and 4,204 teachers were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The study revealed a high level of administrative effectiveness (overall weighted mean = 3.47) among principals in planning (weighted mean = 3.48), coordinating (weighted mean = 3.39), and supervising (weighted mean = 3.47) activities in their schools. However, areas for improvement were identified, such as ensuring the provision of necessary resources, planning for maintenance of school infrastructural facilities, and deciding how the school budget will be spent. The prevalence of autocratic leadership (44.5%) among public secondary school principals in Oyo State was also found, but a significant proportion reported using democratic and digital leadership styles. The findings from the study indicate that there is a significantly high positive relationship ($r = 0.958$) between leadership styles and administrative effectiveness. The study suggested among others that there is a need for principals to explore alternative leadership styles that promote teamwork, collaboration, and shared decision-making.

Keywords: Principals' Leadership Styles and Public Senior Secondary Schools, Administrative Effectiveness

1. Introduction

The success of an organization heavily relies on its administrative effectiveness, which refers to the proactive measures taken by its leaders to achieve the organization's goals. Administrative effectiveness is usually evaluated based on the output it produces, and it involves the optimal utilization of both human and material resources to meet organizational objectives. It is achieved by implementing efficient practices, innovative techniques, and appropriate technology to streamline operations, increase productivity, and make the most of available resources to attain desired goals (Jideofor 2020). Administrative effectiveness requires effective planning, coordinating, supervising, organizing, and directing to achieve the required results. However, this study focused on planning, coordinating and supervision.

Planning is an important role in businesses because it helps with goal-setting, resource allocation, and the breakdown of steps needed to achieve those goals. According to Orefice and Guraziu (2018), planning is recognized as one of the essential operations that play an important role in improving the policies, plans, and means that are organized to select the best solutions to attain certain goals given the varied organizational resources. Planning is essential for achieving administrative effectiveness in an organization because it allows for the clarification of goals, the allocation of resources, the anticipation of potential challenges, increased efficiency, improved decision-making, accountability, and the promotion of innovations.

Coordinating refers to the act of bringing together and managing the efforts of different individuals or groups to achieve a common goal. This management tool is essential for fostering collaboration and communication within an organization, particularly in schools where administrative work needs to be effective to meet organizational goals. To achieve a specific objective, the coordinating process involves synchronizing and integrating various activities, functions, or processes in an organization. This is done by systematically linking the objectives, activities, and strategies of different departments or functional units. By working together, individuals with complementary skills and resources can produce high-quality products within a specified timeframe, thus helping organizations achieve their objectives (Ayeni&Akinfolarin, 2014).

To ensure that tasks are executed according to established standards, norms, or expectations, supervision is necessary. In order to guarantee that workers are working effectively and efficiently, overseeing frequently consists of a manager or administrator supervising subordinates and providing direction, guidance, and help. Giving clear instructions and feedback, establishing goals and expectations, keeping track of progress, presenting opportunities for training and advancement, and resolving performance issues as they occur are all part of it.

For the effective administration of a school, the principal is responsible for the execution of the school curriculum and the smooth operation of the school to obtain high productivity from the staff in terms of effective teaching and learning. Jideofor (2020) stated that the principal as an administrator is to provide teachers with sound instructional leadership, supportive staff personnel/services, thorough instructional supervision, good motivation, effective communication system where teachers are actively involved in decision-making and actively participating in planning and evaluating the instructional programme. Thus this study explores the influence principal's leadership style on the determinant of administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

A leader is someone who motivates others to achieve planned or specified goals. A leader is also someone who is in charge of persuading followers and influencing their attitudes, conduct, and sentiment in order to successfully accomplish stated goals and objectives. According to Belias, Rossidis, Papademetriou and Mantas (2022), a leader uses a mix of characteristics, qualities, and behaviours that make up their leadership style to guide others, inspire employees, and carry out plans. Several leadership philosophies, including authoritarian, democratic, strategic, pace-setting, digital, servant, laissez-faire, transactional, transformational, coaching, situational, bureaucratic, and visionary leadership exists, however, autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital leadership styles will be taken into account in this study, especially as they relate to the administrative effectiveness of principals.

The autocratic leader controls with an iron hand, and subordinates of an autocratic leader don't participate in decision-making (Siddique & Siddique 2019; Akparep, Jengre&Mogre 2019; Lundmark, Richter &Tafvelin 2022). Autocratic leadership styles typically fail to provide an explanation for their behaviour and are uncompromising in their position (Du, Li. & Luo 2020; Dai & Spires 2018). It is one in which the leader holds a disproportionate amount of decision-making authority. In this style of leadership, the leader's power is consolidated, and virtually all decisions about objectives, tasks, projects, and work procedures are made by the leader. They force all work practises and procedures on their staff members and refuse to give them authority over significant decisions. The majority of jobs are rigidly structured and highly organised. Talking about creativity and unorthodox thought is essentially impossible. Declahanov, Bozorou and Sung 2019 argued that as a result of authoritarian leadership, innovative ideas might be suppressed in organisations.

The democratic leadership style comprises the leader delegating decision-making authority to group members while simultaneously advancing social equality and the group's goals. A democratic leader makes choices after considering the opinions of all team members. Each employee has a voice in the direction the project takes, even though he or she makes the final decision (Peretomode 2012). This leadership approach seems to be one of the most successful since it fosters lower-level employees' involvement in the decision-making process. If a principal thinks that staff members need to be heard, then that principal is said to have chosen a democratic leadership style in the educational system. Even if their proposals are not followed through on, the staff still feels valued if their thoughts are taken into consideration; it is acknowledged that this is a step in the decision-making process.

Laissez-faire leadership, commonly referred to as hands-off leadership, includes the leader delegating decision-making authority to subordinates but offering little supervision or oversight. Its origins can be found in the French proverb "Laissez-faire" which translates to "let them do." In this leadership style, the boss gives workers the freedom to assume responsibility for their tasks, including making decisions and finding solutions on their own. A laissez-faire leadership style completely gives the followers rights and decision-making authority (Schultz & Schultz, 2010). Laissez-faire managers grant their employees complete freedom in how they carry out their duties. It enables followers to exercise self-governance while still offering direction and assistance when necessary. Lee and Ding 2020 stated that although the laissez-faire leader who practises guided freedom provides all the resources needed for the followers to accomplish their goals, he or she does not take part in decision-making until the followers ask for it.

In the digital era, digital leadership is a desired leadership style (Gartner, 2018). Digital leadership uses technology, such as digital devices, services, and resources, to improve communication, plan work and personal lives, and develop innovative approaches to accomplishing things well that have been done before (Bakare&Oredein, 2020). They view technology as the equivalent of money (Promsri, 2019). A digital leader inspires their team members to share their curiosity and is continually looking for the best and most inventive ways to perform tasks (Bakare &Oredein 2020). They typically work hard to find time for studying and frequently have an open mind. They ensure that their work is interesting, pertinent, fundable, available, and reasonably priced to produce and deliver (Promsri, 2019). A good digital leader is aware of the company's objectives and knows how their duties fit into those goals. Birgit and Alptekin (2018) agreed that with a significant emphasis on changes in the competitive market, it is a team-oriented job with a cooperative approach.

2. Statement of the Problem

In recent years, there has been a widespread feeling of discontent with the administrative effectiveness of most public secondary school principals in Nigeria, especially in Oyo State. This is evidenced by low levels of teacher job performance, a lack of discipline among students and staff, poor record-keeping and inadequate coordination of admission and examination procedures. Additionally, there are low levels of academic attainment and performance among students, and teacher job satisfaction and dedication seem to be in a state of bemisery. These issues suggest that public secondary schools with incompetent principals lacking digital knowledge and suitable leadership styles may struggle to achieve their educational goals. Previous studies have identified various factors that contribute to this, including poor working environments, non-digitalized principals, poor decision-making skills, bad government policies, insufficient teacher cooperation and staffing, and inadequate funding (Friedländer, Röber& Schaefer, 2021). However, there is still much work to be done in exploring the impact of leadership styles on the administrative effectiveness of public senior secondary school principals in Oyo State. Therefore, this study aims to investigate how leadership styles can influence the administrative effectiveness of public senior secondary school principals in Oyo State.

3. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between leadership styles and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to:

1. assess the level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) of public secondary school principals in Oyo State.
2. identify the prevalent leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital leadership) that is being adopted by public secondary school administrators in Oyo State.
3. examine the relationship between leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Oyo State.

4. Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, the following research questions are posed to be answered.

1. What is the level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) among public secondary school principals in Oyo State?
2. What is the most prevalent leadership style (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital) among public secondary school principals in Oyo State?

5. Hypothesis

H₀₁: There will be no significant relationship between leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital), and administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State

6. Methodology

6.1. Research Design

The descriptive research design of survey type was used for this study, this is because the variables of interest in the study have been identified and the researcher has no control over them or cannot manipulate them. Also, the design is considered appropriate because the existing characteristics of leadership styles and administrative effectiveness of principals were described.

6.2. Selection of Participants

A multistage sampling procedure using stratified and simple random sampling techniques was used to arrive at a reliable sample to represent the population of the study. In the first stage, Oyo State was stratified into three using the existing senatorial districts, which are Oyo Central, North and South senatorial districts. Secondly, in each of the strata, local governments with the highest and lowest number of schools were selected. In the case of two local governments having the same number of schools, the one with the highest number of teachers was selected. In the third stage, Yamane formula was used to determine number of sample size of teachers for each of the selected local governments. These teachers were selected using Simple Random Sampling technique. The Local Government Area with the least number of teachers was used as a baseline for the selection of the teachers having a total of 4,204 respondents (teachers) and all the principals (629) of the selected schools as well.

6.3. Ethical Consideration

Ethical guideline relating to data collection, analysis and interpretation on research as specified by Lead City University was followed.

6.4. Analysis of Data

Data collected from the field were analyzed using inferential and descriptive statistics. The descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage and mean and standard deviation were used for research questions while inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used for the hypothesis.

7. Results

7.1. Research Question One

What is the level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state?

Table 1: Level of administrative effectiveness (planning, coordinating and supervision) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state.

S/N	Items	Always	Often	Rarely	Never	Mean	SD
		Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)	Freq Per(%)		
Planning							
1	ensures academic activities are planned early before the commencement of the term.	3227 (82.6%)	557 (14.3%)	114 (2.9%)	10 (0.3%)	3.79	.489
2	ensures provision of human resources needed for smooth operation in the school	2254 (57.5%)	1422 (36.3%)	236 (6.0%)	6 (0.2%)	3.51	.616
3	ensures provision of materials resources needed for smooth operation in the school	2254 (57.5%)	1294 (33.0%)	360 (9.2%)	10 (0.3%)	3.48	.670
4	calls stakeholders meeting when planning school activities	2059 (52.6%)	1399 (35.7%)	324 (8.3%)	136 (3.5%)	3.37	.780
5	plans for maintenance of school infrastructural facilities	1994 (50.9%)	1540 (39.3%)	322 (8.2%)	62 (1.6%)	3.40	.706
6	plans for co-curricular activities	2317 (59.1%)	1268 (32.4%)	307 (7.8%)	26 (0.7%)	3.50	.668
7	sets discipline policy at this school	2613 (66.7%)	949 (24.2%)	336 (8.6%)	20 (0.5%)	3.57	.669
8	decide how school budget will be spent	1916 (48.9%)	1218 (31.1%)	506 (12.9%)	278 (7.1%)	3.22	.924
Weighted Mean						3.48	
Coordination							
1	create and implement shared school vision	1616 (41.2%)	1752 (44.7%)	466 (11.9%)	81 (2.1%)	3.26	.759
2	nurture and sustain a culture and instructional program conducive to learning and staff development	1648 (42.1%)	1791 (45.7%)	416 (10.6%)	63 (1.6%)	3.28	.715
3	ensures management of school operations to produce a safe and effective learning environment	2263 (57.8%)	1301 (33.2%)	331 (8.4%)	23 (0.6%)	3.48	.674
4	collaborates with families and the diverse communities that schools serve	1524 (38.9%)	1730 (44.2%)	487 (12.4%)	177 (4.5%)	3.17	.815
5	promotes integrity, fairness, and ethical behavior	2561 (65.4%)	987 (25.2%)	308 (7.9%)	62 (1.6%)	3.54	.707
6	interacts with government agencies on school matters	1928 (49.2%)	1334 (34.0%)	556 (14.2%)	100 (2.6%)	3.30	.804
7	coordinates all units or departments in the school to achieve synergy	2396 (61.3%)	1123 (28.7%)	288 (7.4%)	101 (2.6%)	3.49	.743

8	encourages team spirit among teachers and other school staff	2560 (65.3%)	1066 (27.2%)	239 (6.1%)	53 (1.4%)	3.57	.670
Weighted Mean						3.39	
Supervision							
1	ensures teachers write lesson plan/note	2823 (72.1%)	839 (21.4%)	186 (4.7%)	70 (1.8%)	3.64	.658
2	visits teachers in the classroom	1900 (48.5%)	1429 (36.5%)	523 (13.3%)	66 (1.7%)	3.32	.765
3	ensures resources in the school are used for the right purpose	2146 (54.8%)	1465 (37.4%)	301 (7.7%)	6 (0.2%)	3.47	.642
4	monitors teachers and other staff's punctuality	2658 (67.8%)	968 (24.7%)	226 (5.8%)	66 (1.7%)	3.59	.677
5	ensures teaching is in accordance with the curriculum	2674 (68.2%)	1024 (26.1%)	195 (5.0%)	25 (0.6%)	3.62	.611
6	ensures standard of examination in the school	2557 (65.3%)	1145 (29.2%)	198 (5.1%)	18 (0.5%)	3.59	.608
7	maintains student/staff discipline	2625 (67.0%)	1000 (25.5%)	254 (6.5%)	39 (1.0%)	3.59	.657
Weighted Mean						3.54	
Overall Weighted Mean						3.47	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Decision Rule: 0 – 1.49= Very Low, 1.50 - 2.49= Low, 2.5 – 3.49 = High, 3.50 –4.0 = Very High

The study aimed to assess the level of administrative effectiveness among public secondary school principals in Oyo state by examining their planning, coordinating, and supervising abilities. The data collected from the principals through a survey was tabulated in Table 1. The findings of the study revealed that the principals were effective in planning activities for the school, as most respondents (82.6%) reported that they always ensure academic activities are planned early before the commencement of the term. However, their effectiveness in ensuring provision of human and material resources needed for smooth operation in the school was rated lower, with 57.5% of respondents reporting they always ensure provision of human resources, and 57.5% also reporting they always ensure provision of material resources. Regarding coordination, the principals reported being effective in promoting integrity, fairness, and ethical behaviour (65.4%) and in coordinating all units or departments in the school to achieve synergy (61.3%). However, creating and implementing shared school vision (41.2%) and nurturing a culture and instructional program conducive to learning and staff development (42.1%) were rated as areas needing improvement. The principals' effectiveness in supervision was rated high. Coordinates all units or departments in the school to achieve synergy: 61.3% of the principals reported always coordinating all units or departments in the school to achieve synergy, while 28.7% often coordinate, 7.4% rarely coordinate, and 2.6% never coordinate. The weighted mean for this item was 3.49, indicating that the principals were relatively effective in this area. Encourages team spirit among teachers and other school staff: 65.3% of the principals reported always encouraging team spirit among teachers and other school staff, while 27.2% often encourage, 6.1% rarely encourage, and 1.4% never encourage. The weighted mean for this item was 3.57, indicating that the principals were relatively effective in this area. Overall, the study found that the level of administrative effectiveness among public secondary school principals in Oyo state was relatively high, with a weighted mean score of 3.48 for planning, 3.39 for coordination, and 3.58 for supervision. However, there were areas for improvement, particularly in ensuring the provision of human and material resources for smooth school operation, calling stakeholders meeting when planning school activities, planning for maintenance of school infrastructural facilities, and deciding how school budget will be spent.

7.2. Research Question Two

What is the most prevalent leadership style (Autocratic, Democratic, Laissez-faire, and Digital) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state?

Table 2: The most prevalent leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital) among public secondary school principals in Oyo state

	Most of the Time	Some of the Times	Seldom	Never	
Items	Freq Per (%)	Freq Per (%)	Freq Per (%)	Freq Per (%)	Mean
Autocratic	1746.25 (44.575)	1507.75 (38.475)	434.5 (11.1)	229.5 (5.85)	3.22
Digital	1350.5 (34.45)	1568.5 (40.05)	645.75 (16.5)	353.25 (9.025)	3.00
Democratic	1216.5 (31.05)	1474 (37.625)	479 (12.2)	748.5 (19.1)	2.81
Laissez-faire	767 (19.575)	1543 (39.375)	578 (14.775)	1030 (26.275)	2.52

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Based on the findings presented in Table 2, the most prevalent leadership style among public secondary school principals in Oyo state varies depending on the style. The table indicates that autocratic leadership is the most prevalent style, with 44.575% of respondents indicating that they use this style most of the time. Digital leadership is the second most prevalent style, with 34.45% of respondents indicating that they use this style most of the time, followed by democratic leadership with 31.05% of respondents indicating that they use this style most of the time. Finally, laissez-faire leadership is the least prevalent style, with only 19.575% of respondents indicating that they use this style most of the time. It is worth noting that while autocratic leadership is the most prevalent style among public secondary school principals in Oyo state, it is not used exclusively, as a significant proportion of respondents reported using democratic and digital leadership styles some of the time. This suggests that there may be a degree of flexibility in the leadership styles employed by public secondary school principals in Oyo state. Overall, these findings provide insight into the prevailing leadership styles among public secondary school principals in Oyo state, which can inform efforts to improve educational leadership and management in the state.

7.3. Testing of Hypothesis

H₀₁: There will be no significant relationship between leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, and digital) and administrative effectiveness of public secondary schools' principals in Oyo state.

		Correlation	
		Administrative Effectiveness	Leadership Styles
Administrative Effectiveness		1	.958**
Leadership Styles		.958**	1

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The findings in the table suggest that there is a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.958$) between leadership styles and the administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State, despite the initial

hypothesis (H_0) that there would be no significant relationship. However, it can be concluded that leadership styles have a unique relationship with administrative effectiveness.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings suggest that the principals were effective in planning activities for the school, coordinating all units or departments in the school to achieve synergy, and encouraging team spirit among teachers and other school staff. However, there were areas identified for improvement, particularly in ensuring the provision of human and material resources needed for smooth operation in the school, creating and implementing shared school vision, and nurturing a culture and instructional program conducive to learning and staff development. The study highlights the importance of addressing these areas to enhance the overall effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo state. These findings could serve as a basis for policy recommendations to improve the quality of education in Oyo state and other parts of Nigeria.

The study also sheds light on the prevailing leadership styles among public secondary school principals in Oyo state. The findings suggest that autocratic leadership is the most prevalent style, followed by digital and democratic leadership, with laissez-faire leadership being the least prevalent style. It is important to note that the principals do not use one leadership style exclusively, indicating a certain degree of flexibility in their leadership approaches. These findings provide valuable insights for improving educational leadership and management in Oyo state and can serve as a basis for developing appropriate leadership training and development programs for school principals. The study also underscores the need for further research to explore the factors that influence the choice of leadership styles among school principals in Oyo state and other parts of Nigeria.

Test of hypothesis indicated that leadership styles significantly influence the administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo state, contrary to the initial hypothesis. These results could have implications for educational policy and practice in the state and beyond.

9. Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study are presented in the table; its aim is to assess the level of administrative effectiveness among public secondary school principals in Oyo state. Research question one examines the level of administrative effectiveness by examining their planning, coordinating, and supervising abilities. The findings indicate both strengths and areas for improvement in the principals' effectiveness. In a study by Pardosi and Utari (2022), they found that effective planning positively influences student achievement. Their findings align with the current study, which reported that a majority of respondents (82.6%) acknowledged the importance of planning academic activities early before the term begins. This high percentage indicates a shared understanding among educators that proactive planning contributes to successful academic outcomes. Furthermore, the present study identified coordination as a critical dimension in school management. The importance of creating and implementing a shared school vision was recognized by 41.2% of the respondents. This finding resonates with the research conducted by Zina (2017), who emphasized the significance of a shared vision in promoting collaboration and alignment of goals among school stakeholders. The moderate level of agreement (mean score: 3.26) in the present study suggests that there is room for improvement in fostering a stronger shared vision among participants. Another aspect of coordination highlighted in the current study is the emphasis on integrity, fairness, and ethical behavior within the school community. This finding aligns with the research by Neal, Justice and Barron (2019), who found that promoting ethical behavior positively impacts the school climate and student engagement. The relatively high agreement (65.4%) and mean score (3.54) in the present study demonstrate the importance placed on ethical values in school management. In terms of supervision, the present study emphasizes the significance of ensuring teachers write lesson plans/notes (72.1%) and maintaining punctuality among school staff (67.8%). These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Pardosi and Utari, (2021), which emphasized the positive impact of effective supervision practices on teacher performance and student achievement. The high agreement percentages and mean scores for these items in the present study further emphasize their importance in ensuring a conducive learning environment.

Research question two provides insights into the most prevalent leadership among public secondary school principals in Oyo State. The study examined four leadership styles: Autocratic, Digital, Democratic, and Laissez-faire. The findings indicate that the Autocratic leadership style was reported to be most prevalent, with a frequency of 44.575%. This finding is consistent with previous research highlighting the prevalence of autocratic leadership in educational settings (Daniëls, Hondeghem, & Dochy, 2019). Autocratic leadership is characterized by centralized decision-making and limited input from subordinates, with the leader making decisions and setting directions unilaterally. While autocratic leadership may provide quick decision-making and clarity in certain situations, it can limit participation, creativity, and ownership among staff members (Abdullatef, 2019). On the other hand, the Digital leadership style, with a frequency of 34.45%, was reported to be somewhat prevalent. Digital leadership refers to leadership practices that embrace technology and digital tools to enhance communication, collaboration, and instructional practices (Gedifew, 2022). The emergence of digital leadership reflects the changing landscape of education and the need for leaders to leverage technology effectively. Digital leadership can facilitate connectivity, knowledge sharing, and innovation among staff and students, leading to enhanced learning experiences (Elrehail, 2018). The findings also indicate that the Democratic leadership style, characterized by shared decision-making and involvement of stakeholders, was reported to be moderately prevalent (31.05%). Democratic leadership emphasizes collaboration, inclusiveness, and participatory decision-making processes (Mburuki & Thinguri 2022). This finding aligns with previous research highlighting the positive impact of democratic leadership on school climate, teacher motivation, and student engagement (Wina Novita, Sulaiman & Muhyani Rizalie 2022). By involving teachers, staff, and other stakeholders in decision-making processes, democratic leadership can foster a sense of ownership, empowerment, and commitment to the school's goals. Lastly, the Laissez-faire leadership style, with a frequency of 19.575%, was reported to be relatively less prevalent. Laissez-faire leadership is characterized by a hands-off approach, where leaders provide minimal guidance or direction to subordinates (Zhang, Wang & Gao 2023). This leadership style can lead to ambiguity, lack of accountability, and reduced organizational effectiveness (Mburuki & Thinguri 2022). However, in certain contexts where there is a high level of expertise and self-motivation among staff members, a laissez-faire approach can foster autonomy and innovation (Zhang, 2023).

Test on hypothesis on significant relationship between leadership styles and administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals in Oyo State. The correlation coefficient of .958** between administrative effectiveness and leadership styles indicates a strong positive relationship between these two variables. This finding suggests that the leadership styles employed within an educational setting significantly influence the administrative effectiveness of the school. When leadership styles align with administrative effectiveness, it can lead to improved organizational outcomes, enhanced staff performance, and positive student experiences. Previous research has also highlighted the importance of leadership styles in determining administrative effectiveness in educational settings. For example, a study by (Krishnan, 2004) found that transformational leadership, characterized by inspiring and motivating followers, was positively correlated with administrative effectiveness. Transformational leaders have been shown to foster a positive work climate, enhance staff satisfaction, and promote innovative practices (Masood & Afsar, 2017). Another related study by Elrehail (2018) examined the impact of transactional leadership, characterized by contingent rewards and punishment, on administrative effectiveness. The results indicated a positive correlation between transactional leadership and administrative effectiveness, suggesting that leaders who provide clear expectations and rewards for performance can positively influence organizational outcomes. Furthermore, research by Zhang, Wang & Gao (2023) explored the relationship between laissez-faire leadership, characterized by a lack of guidance and involvement, and administrative effectiveness. The findings revealed a negative correlation between laissez-faire leadership and administrative effectiveness, indicating that a hands-off approach to leadership can hinder organizational success and staff performance. The high correlation coefficient of .958** in the current study underscores the importance of leadership styles in shaping administrative effectiveness. It suggests that leaders who adopt effective leadership styles, such as transformational or transactional leadership, are more likely to contribute to the overall effectiveness of the administration. On the other hand, ineffective leadership styles, such as laissez-faire leadership, can have detrimental effects on administrative effectiveness.

10. Recommendations

1. There is a need for develop training programs to improve principals' ability to ensure provision of human and material resources needed for smooth operation in the school. This could involve providing training on budgeting and resource allocation, as well as identifying and leveraging available resources. The training should be designed to address the areas where principals rated themselves lower, such as ensuring provision of human and material resources.
2. Government should foster a culture of shared vision and continuous learning by creating opportunities for principals to collaborate and learn from each other. This could include establishing peer learning networks, promoting a culture of continuous improvement, and facilitating ongoing professional development opportunities. This would help principals to improve their ability to create and implement a shared school vision, nurture a culture and instructional program conducive to learning and staff development, and call stakeholders meetings when planning school activities.
3. There is a need for periodic develop training programs for public secondary school principals in Oyo state. The training should focus on developing a range of leadership styles. The training should aim to enhance the skills and knowledge of school principals in using democratic and digital leadership styles, which were also found to be prevalent. This will help to increase the flexibility and adaptability of principals in responding to different situations, and to develop their capacity to lead their schools towards improved educational outcomes. The training could also include opportunities for principals to share their experiences and learn from one another.
4. Public secondary school principals in Oyo state should be encouraged to adopt a balanced approach to leadership that incorporates different leadership styles. This can be achieved by providing leadership training and coaching that focuses on developing the skills and knowledge required to effectively use different leadership styles in different situations. This approach will enable school principals to be more flexible and adaptable in responding to different challenges and circumstances, and to leverage the strengths of each leadership style to improve administrative effectiveness in their schools.
5. It is also recommended that future research be conducted to investigate the unique influence of each leadership style on administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Oyo state, to provide a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between leadership and school effectiveness.

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